

Characterisation of Pyrophosphato Complexes of Cu(II), Ni(II), Co(II), and Fe(III)

C. L. SHARMA*, A. K. SINGH and M. P. SINGH

Department of Chemistry, University of Roorkee,
Roorkee.

Manuscript received 3 May 1976; revised 28 June 1976;
accepted 9 July 1976

DETAILED studies on the composition and stability of the interaction products of pyrophosphate ions with various multivalent cations¹⁻⁵ have been made. In the present note we report the structure and ligand field parameters of pyrophosphato complexes of Cu(II), Ni(II), Co(II) and Fe(III).

Experimental

All the reagents used were of A.R. quality and physical measurements were the same as reported earlier⁶.

The complexes were prepared by mixing the 0.2M solution of metal salts and disodium dihydrogen pyrophosphate keeping a slight excess of the latter in order to get a 1 : 2 (M : P) complex. The precipitates formed were filtered, washed several times with 50% alcohol and then dried in a desiccator over sulphuric acid.

- (i) Found : Cu, 13.11%, P₂O₇, 72.32%, Calc. for Na₂ [Cu(H₂P₂O₇)₂] H₂O : Cu, 13.25% ; P₂O₇, 72.57%.
- (ii) Found : Ni, 11.39% ; P₂O₇, 68.00%, Calc. for Na₂ [Ni(H₂P₂O₇)₂] (H₂O)₂ H₂O : Ni, 11.49%, P₂O₇, 68.14%.
- (iii) Found : Co, 11.45%, P₂O₇, 67.81% Calc. for Na₂ [Co(H₂P₂O₇)₂] (H₂O)₂, H₂O : Co, 11.53%, P₂O₇, 68.10%.
- (iv) Found : Fe, 11.41% ; P₂O₇, 71.35%, Calc. for Na[Fe(H₂P₂O₇)₂] (H₂O)₂ 2H₂O : Fe, 11.52% ; P₂O₇, 71.77%.

The molar conductance (0.001M aqueous solutions) of Fe(III) complex was found 90 mhos while that of Cu(II), Ni(II) and Co(II) complexes were found 288 mhos which indicated the presence of two and three ions respectively.

Results and Discussion

The electronic spectrum of Co(II) complex gave a main band at 23809 cm⁻¹ (ν₃) and two shoulders at 18182 cm⁻¹ (ν₂) and 12300 cm⁻¹ (ν₁). The value of 10 Dq, B and β (Nephelauxetic ratio) was thus found to be 13705, cm⁻¹, 861 cm⁻¹ and 0.88 respectively. The spectrum of an aqueous solution of Ni(II) complex gave three absorption bands at ν₁ = 10000 cm⁻¹, ν₂ = 15700 cm⁻¹ and ν₃ = 26315 cm⁻¹ which is the characteristic feature of an octahedral structure. The value of 10 Dq, B and β was found to be 10000 cm⁻¹, 801 cm⁻¹ and 0.77 respectively. The ν₂/ν₁ of the complex was 1.57 which was also typical of six coordinate

geometry about Ni(II)⁷ One shoulder corresponding to 14000 cm⁻¹ was also obtained perhaps due to non-identical donor atoms indicating a slight geometrical distortion. The absorption spectra of the pale complex of iron gave a double peak at 12000 cm⁻¹ and bluish white complex of copper gave two bands at 13890 cm⁻¹ and 26000 cm⁻¹.

Cu(II), Ni(II), Co(II) and Fe(III) complexes were found paramagnetic with a magnetic moment of 1.87, 2.90, 5.00 and 5.90 B.M. respectively.

The main characteristic feature of the i.r. spectra was the shifting of ν (P-O-Na) at 1120 cm⁻¹ and ν(O-P-O) at 580 cm⁻¹ (Disodium dihydrogen phosphate) to 1080 cm⁻¹ and 540 cm⁻¹ (metal complexes) respectively which indicated the coordination of the metal through oxygen. The stretching bands due to water molecules at 3400 cm⁻¹ and 1640 cm⁻¹ and due to P-O-P at 940 cm⁻¹ were obtained in the spectra of all the complexes.

References

1. L. B. ROGERS and C. A. REYNOLDS, *J. Amer. Chem. Soc.*, 1949, 71, 2081.
2. R. S. SUBRAHMANYA, *J. Indian, Inst. Sci.*, 1956, 38A, 87.
3. J. I. WALTERS and I. M. KOLTHOFF, *J. Amer. Chem. Soc.*, 1948, 70, 2455.
4. J. VAID and T. L. RAMACHAR, *Current Sci.*, 1954, 23, 396.
5. B. C. HALDAR, *Nature*, 1950, 166, 744.
6. W. U. MALIK, C. L. SHARMA, M. C. JAIN and Y. ASHRAF, *J. Inorg. Nuclear. Chem.*, 1971, 33, 4333.
7. L. SACCONI, "Transition Metal Chemistry", Vol. 4, (Ed) R. L. CARLIN. Merce! Dekker, Inc., New York, 1968, p. 216.

Studies on the Succinimide Complexes of Pd(II), Au(III), Pt(IV), Ce(IV) and Th(IV)

C. L. SHARMA* and SAVITA SHARMA

Department of Chemistry, University of Roorkee,
Roorkee.

Manuscript received 3 May 1976; revised 28 June 1976;
accepted 9 July 1976.

The simple and mixed ligand complexes of succinimide with common transition elements have been studied by several workers¹⁻⁵. In this note we deal with the composition, stability and structure of Pd(II), Au(III), Pt(IV), Ce(IV) and Th(IV) succinimide complexes.

Experimental

The chlorides of Pd(II), Au(III), Pt(V), K(I); nitrates of Ce(IV), Th(IV), K(I) and all other reagents used were of A.R. grade. The solution of PdCl₂ was prepared in 0.2M, HCl and of others in double distilled water.

*Senior author